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Educational Trends in the Jewish Population: Long-Term Patterns by Ethnic Groups

Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein

Introduction

The research literature in Israel is rich in documenting socioeconomic gaps between origin groups in Jewish society. Dahan (2016) showed that the relevance of origin is not limited to the political arena but is also evident in other domains such as the legal system, institutions of higher education, cultural institutions, and television broadcasting. Israel Prize laureate in sociology, Professor Sami Samuha, spoke on this topic in 2023 and argued that the ethnic divide remains central to Jewish social life. In his view, this problem will persist for generations (Makover-Belikov, 2023). However, survey results from the Israeli Democracy Index of the Israel Democracy Institute are especially noteworthy. Respondents were asked, "Which tension in Israeli society do you consider the strongest today?" The possible answers were: between Right and Left; between religious and secular; between Jews and Arabs; between rich and poor; between Mizrahim and Ashkenazim. Between 2012 and 2024, fewer than 5% of Jews answered that the tension between Mizrahim (of Asian/African descent) and Ashkenazim (of European/American descent) was the strongest (Hermann et al., 2025, p. 211). However, one should remember that there remains a correlation between origin and voting patterns (Dahan, 2023), which finds expression in the prominent tension between the political Right and Left in Israeli society.

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Over the past three decades, significant changes have occurred in the demographic structure of Jewish society in Israel, and as a result, similar changes have taken place in the composition of students in the education system. Most students in the Jewish education system are 2nd and 3rd generation descendants of immigrants from Europe or America (Ashkenazim) and from Asia or Africa (Mizrahim), to which large numbers of children from the former Soviet Union (FSU) have been added, and, to a lesser extent, children of immigrants from Ethiopia.

In the 1990s, dramatic changes took place in Israel's education system. Reforms were made to the Bagrut (matriculation) exams with the primary aim of raising the eligibility rates for the Bagrut certificate — particularly among weaker socioeconomic strata — and a widespread process of establishing higher-education institutions began. Within this framework, state-funded regional colleges were founded and expanded, private colleges opened, and branches of foreign universities were established. These policy measures contributed to the increase in Bagrut eligibility rates and to the growth of the population seeking higher education (Bar-Haim et al., 2013; Koprak, 2022).

Investment in education is one of the principal tools for addressing the high economic inequality characteristic of Israeli society. According to Human Capital Theory, investment in education — alongside the experience an individual gains through on-the-job training — increases a worker's productivity and their earning capacity (Becker, 1962).¹ Investment in higher education encourages innovation, increases employment, and improves productivity and wages in ways that bolster economic growth (Hanushek, 2016). The expansion of higher education contributes to social mobility and the reduction of economic and social gaps in various aspects — such as income, health, and poverty reduction (Chernichovsky et al., 2017; Dahan, 2016; Gordon et al., 2022; Hofmarcher, 2021).

This research focuses on the expansion of education among origin groups in Jewish society in Israel over three decades (1995–2023). It examines trends in overall education levels, trends among those with higher education, and trends in study majors for academic degrees.

1 Vocational training at the place of work includes training specific to a job position or more general training.

Literature review

There is broad consensus in Israeli society that education is the key to success in life and that equal opportunity in access to education must be ensured for all children in Israel. Several central explanations have been offered for the educational inequality between origin groups in Jewish society in Israel.

1. Tracking in the education system. In the wake of the early immigration waves to the young State, the Ministry of Education believed that immigrant children — particularly those arriving from North African and Middle Eastern countries — would be unable to meet the academic demands of a general (theoretical) curriculum. Accordingly, it was decided to direct them to vocational tracks and schools that emphasized professional training and imposed lower academic requirements.

Proponents of vocational education argued that it contributed by reducing dropout rates; created relatively homogeneous learning groups, facilitating more efficient teaching; provided a safety net that lowered the risk of unemployment and poverty, thereby boosting future earning capacity for lower socioeconomic populations; narrowed socioeconomic gaps while fostering social solidarity; and supplied skilled labor force for various sectors of the economy during the State's early years of rapid development. Critics countered that vocational tracks distanced students from the Bagrut exams — a prerequisite for higher education — and steered graduates into low-wage, low-status occupations. By contrast, the general studies track led to a Bagrut certificate, prepared students for academic study, and opened doors to prestigious professions and higher social standing. Another critique holds that, in an era of rapid technological change and high occupational mobility, the specific human capital acquired in vocational training can quickly become obsolete. More broadly, this view questions the advisability of investing in vocational education versus general education, which imparts a wider general knowledge base, given that job-specific skills can be acquired on the job. In sum, the tracking process in the education system has served to perpetuate social disparities since the State's founding, undermined future equality of opportunity in both education and quality employment, and diminished social mobility (Ayalon et al., 2019; Blank et al., 2015; Feniger et al., 2013; Ministry of Finance, 2017; Shavit, 2013; Shay & Zussman, 2010; Weissblei, 2018).

Research among non-Haredi (non-ultra-Orthodox) Jews born in 1974–1978 shows that intergenerational income mobility is lower for Mizrahim than for Ashkenazim, with the principal source of the gap being unequal educational opportunities (Heller, 2020).² Among the sharpest critics of tracking was Shlomo Swirski, who viewed it as a mechanism for perpetuating Ashkenazi relative advantage through ethnic separation and the exclusion of Mizrahim from strong schools and rewarding occupations (Swirski, 1990, quoted in Shavit, 2013).

By the late 1970s, more than half of high school students were enrolled in vocational education (Vurgan & Nathan, 2008). Mizrahi students were vastly overrepresented in the vocational track, whereas their representation in the general studies track leading to Bagrut eligibility was very low (Shavit, 2013). Another study finds that from the early 1970s to the mid-1980s there was a marked narrowing of the Bagrut eligibility gap between Mizrahim and Ashkenazim — though disparities remained substantial (Friedlander et al., 2016, Table 5.1).

Over the years, reforms have reshaped the upper-secondary education system. From the mid-1980s onward, the share of students in the vocational track declined (Feniger et al., 2023), and in the 1990s — due to the negative public image of vocational education — the designation was changed to *technological education*, which was perceived as more prestigious. At the same time, high schools evolved from being clearly general studies or vocational to offering a broad mix of study tracks, alongside an academization of curricula to enable Bagrut certification (Bar-Haim & Feniger, 2022).

Fuchs et al. (2018) examined developments in technological education in the 21st century and showed that between 2006 and 2017 the share of students in technological tracks rose from 33% to 40%.³ The researchers divided students from technological education into three groups by Bagrut exam performance: the technological-engineering track, preparing for Bagrut and further technological study (high); the intermediate technological track (medium),

2 In other words, the earnings of a child of Mizrahi origin are more closely correlated with the family's socioeconomic background than for a child of Ashkenazi origin.

3 In 2017, 68% of students attended comprehensive schools that combined general studies and technological tracks, 21% attended schools offering only general studies, and 10% attended technological schools. These calculations are based on the data in Table 3b in Fuchs et al., 2018.

preparing for Bagrut; and the vocational technological track, focused on vocational training (low).⁴ They found that in Grade 12 the high track's share of technological-education students rose from 31.5% to 36.6%, while the shares of the other two tracks — characterized by lower Bagrut success — declined.⁵

Ultimately, the Ministry of Education succeeded in reducing dropout rates and expanding the technological-engineering track.⁶ Nevertheless, in the intermediate and vocational technological tracks over 60% of technological education students remain enrolled, and their Bagrut certificate attainment is underwhelming (below 50% eligibility).

2. *Residential area.* In 1948, upon the establishment of the State, 650,000 Jews lived in Israel. Following the mass immigration wave of 1951, the Jewish population doubled, and by 1962 it exceeded two million.⁷ Immigrants in those early waves succeeded in settling in central urban areas or their environs. Absorption of later waves of immigrants during the 1950s — mainly from North Africa — was far more complex. The government adopted a population-dispersion policy, directing newcomers to development towns — some existing settlements repurposed for immigrant absorption, and others founded specifically for that purpose, such as Ofakim, Beit She'an, Dimona, Kiryat Shmona, Migdal HaEmek, and others (Benita & Becker, 2018).⁸ These towns provided housing solutions

4 In the technological-engineering track, 98% of students took the Bagrut exams, 84% qualified for a Bagrut certificate, and 27% took the 5-unit Bagrut exams in both mathematics and English; in the intermediate track, 88% took the exams, 46% qualified, and 2% took 5-unit mathematics and English; and in the vocational track, 61% took the exams, 10% qualified, and 0.1% took the 5-unit exams in mathematics and English. These calculations are based on the data in Table 1 in Fuchs et al., 2018.

5 The share of students in the intermediate technological track fell from 59.7% to 56.3%, and the share of the vocational technological track declined from 8.7% to 7%. These calculations are based on the data in Table 2 of Fuchs et al., 2018.

6 Another study by Yanay et al. (2019) examined upper-secondary dropout trends in the 21st century. It found that the decline in dropout rates within technological education was stronger than in general studies education — particularly in the low technological track, where retaining students presents the greatest challenge.

7 Based on a review of the CBS website.

8 The list comprises the following 25 localities: Ofakim, Eilat, Beit She'an, Beit Shemesh, Dimona, Hatzor HaGlilit, Tiberias, Yavne, Yokne'am Illit, Yeruham, Karmiel, Migdal HaEmek, Ma'alot-Tarshiha, Mitzpe Ramon, Nof HaGalil, Netivot, Afula, Acre, Arad, Safed, Kiryat Gat, Kiryat Malakhi, Kiryat Shmona, Sderot, and Shlomi. Sixteen of these are ranked in Clusters 2–4 by the CBS (low to lower-middle socioeconomic status).

for immigrants and contributed to populating the periphery and relieving overcrowding in the central cities (Adler et al., 2005). In the early years, the development towns shared similar characteristics — low socioeconomic status, high unemployment rates, and low educational attainment — but over time social and economic changes created differences among them.

Although the population-dispersion policy achieved its primary goal of settling the land, it failed in the social sense: it produced a clear geographic segregation of different origin groups, concentrating Mizrahim in the socioeconomically weak development towns. This high concentration of Mizrahim, together with limited labor market and educational opportunities, underlies the argument that these towns contributed to the perpetuation of the ethnic gap.

From a historical perspective, educational opportunity inequality between established and less established localities manifested in the distribution of students between the general studies and vocational tracks. More affluent cities offered far more general studies frameworks than less affluent settlements, yet competition for admission to prestigious general studies track was fiercest in the cities — disadvantaging the weaker socioeconomic strata. Ayalon (1992) found that in the less advantaged localities — with their higher share of Mizrahim — students had better chances of admission to general studies tracks than in more affluent cities. The claim is that lower status students find it easier to compete for general studies track placement in less affluent towns, whereas in affluent cities they must compete against more advantaged peers.

In recent years several Israeli studies have examined intergenerational mobility, including empirical analysis of residential location effects. Heller (2020) studied individuals born in 1980–1981 and showed that the stronger the economic standing of the residential environment (both at the locality and high school levels), the better the child's future socioeconomic outcome — and the weaker the intergenerational link (i.e., higher mobility). The study also demonstrates that the higher a school's academic level (measured by Bagrut scores), the greater the children's intergenerational mobility in adulthood.

Batz and Krill (2022) examined non-Haredi Jews born between 1979 and 1983 and found that localities characterized by upward wage mobility also share features such as low geographic periphery status, relatively high levels of education and income among residents, low dependency on transfer payments,

high rates of military enlistment, and low levels of violence.⁹ The towns with the lowest mobility for children (non-Haredi Jews) were: Arad, Afula, Kiryat Shmona, Kiryat Yam, Beit Shemesh, Kiryat Malakhi, Migdal HaEmek, Tiberias, and Safed. In contrast, central-district localities enjoyed the highest mobility — they included Ramat HaSharon, Givatayim, Kiryat Ono, Holon, Herzliya, Ramat Gan, Petah Tikva, Ra'anana, Rishon LeZion, and Yavne.

3. *Socioeconomic background of parents.* The extensive literature links parental education to their children's academic achievements (for a review, see Dobrin, 2015). More educated parents succeed in transmitting their educational advantage to their offspring, who in turn can convert it into their own educational and economic achievements. Dobrin shows, based on data from 2011, that among native-born Israelis aged 25–44 whose parents came from Asia/Africa (2nd generation), 5% of mothers and 7% of fathers held an academic degree, whereas among those whose parents came from Europe/America, 33% of mothers and 39% of fathers held an academic degree (Dobrin, 2015, Figure 2).

It is well known that well-educated families are generally more affluent. Parents with means can help their children navigate academic challenges through investments in private tutoring, purchasing textbooks, acquiring advanced computer, enrolling them in expensive prestigious private institutions, and more. Such parents can also enable their children to attend costly private colleges if they do not gain admission to universities. A study by Bar-Haim et al. (2013) documents a positive relationship between the father's occupational prestige and the likelihood of obtaining a Bagrut certificate and a first academic degree among young adults aged 27–34. Likewise, Feniger et al. (2013) find that, among those born between 1978 and 1982, children of educated parents were more likely to enroll in higher education than children of parents with low education levels. However, these gaps narrowed once high school performance and the psychometric exam were taken into account. In other words, disparities in higher education participation between origin groups may be related to factors such as the quality of the schooling system and the tracking processes.

9 The researchers define upward intergenerational wage mobility as a situation in which children from lower socioeconomic families succeed in climbing the income ladder and improving their relative position compared to their parents at a high rate.

Data and definitions

Data

This study is based on three publicly available databases from the Israel Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS).

Labor Force Survey. A central household survey conducted by the Central Bureau of Statistics. The survey provides ongoing monitoring of developments in Israel's labor force, including its size, characteristics, the extent of unemployment, and more. The data include information on labor force attributes, age, years of schooling, type of last school attended, data on immigrants since 1990, and more (from the CBS website). The data used in this study cover the years 2000–2023, and the analysis was limited to Jews and Others aged 25–64. In 2000–2011, the sample size ranged from 49,000 to 52,000 observations. Beginning in 2012, the sampling methodology shifted from quarterly to monthly measurement, with the annual number of observations in those years ranging from 100,000 to 138,000.

Social Survey. An annual survey that provides up-to-date information on living conditions and well-being in Israel. The Social Survey comprises two main components: a fixed core, containing a large number of questions across various life domains — such as health, housing, employment, education, economic status, computer use, religion and religious observance — and a changing section, dedicated each year to one or two new topics studied in depth (from the CBS website). The data used in this study span 2002–2023 and are limited to Jews and Others aged 25–64. The sample size ranged from 4,000 to 4,600 observations in the various years. Its primary limitation is the smaller sample size compared to the Labor Force Survey; however, it includes a number of variables not available elsewhere.

Population Census. The census is a large-scale statistical operation designed to collect demographic, social, and economic data on the country's population (from the CBS website). The census used in this study is the 1995 census, and the analysis was limited to Jews aged 25–64. The sample size in the 1995 census was 404,000 observations.¹⁰

10 The study also used data from the 1983 Population Census as well. Since that census does not include information on the mother's country or continent of birth, it was employed only for aggregate analyses and not for origin-group comparisons.

Origin groups¹¹

1. *European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)*
 - Europe/America-born (1st generation)
 - Israel-born with parents born in Europe/America (2nd generation)
2. *Israel-born with a parent born in Israel and a parent born in Europe/America (generation 2.5)*
 - Israel-born with a father born in Israel and a mother born in Europe/America
 - Israel-born with a mother born in Israel and father born in Europe/America
3. *Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)*
 - Asia/Africa born (1st generation)
 - Israel-born with parents born in Asia/Africa (2nd generation)
4. *Israel-born with a parent born in Israel and a parent born in Asia/Africa (generation 2.5)*
 - Israel-born with a father born in Israel and a mother born in Asia/Africa
 - Israel-born with a mother born in Israel and a father born in Asia/Africa
5. *Israel-born from a mixed ethnic origin — a parent born in Europe/America and a parent born in Asia/Africa (2nd generation)*
 - Israel-born with a father born in Europe/America and a mother born in Asia/Africa
 - Israel-born with a father born in Asia/Africa and a mother born in Europe/America

11 The construction of the origin variable is based on the continent of birth of the individual, the father, and the mother, which were available for all years in the Labor Force Survey. The variables for the country of birth of the father and mother were not available for years after 2011. Classifying origin groups by continent of birth is not free of bias. For example, individuals who migrated to France from North Africa and then immigrated to Israel will be classified as European-origin (Ashkenazi), even though they identify as Mizrahi; children of immigrants from the former USSR who were born in Israel will be classified as Israel-born whose parents were born in Europe/America (2nd generation) and not as 2nd generation FSU immigrants; children of Ethiopian immigrants will be classified as Israel-born whose parents were born in Asia/Africa (2nd generation) and not as 2nd generation Ethiopian immigrants. It is not possible to isolate Ethiopian-born individuals in the Social Survey, as the identification variable in this survey is based solely on continent of birth.

6. *Israel-born with parents born in Israel (3rd generation)*
7. *Former Soviet Union born and immigrated to Israel in 1990 or since (henceforth: immigrants from the FSU)*
8. *Ethiopian immigrants*

Changes in the population composition by origin group

Table 1 presents the changes in the relative size of the origin groups comprising Jewish society in the years 1995–2023. The data are reported for the main working-age population (ages 25–64).¹² Several notable findings emerge from the data:

- Native-born Israelis whose parents were both born in Israel (3rd generation) have become the largest group, comprising 31% of the population in 2022–2023.¹³ Moreover, there has been growth among native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other born abroad (generation 2.5). These natural shifts mirror the decline in the relative size of Europe/America origin groups (1st and 2nd generations) and Asia/Africa origin groups (1st and 2nd generations).
- Native-born Israelis with one parent born in Europe/America and the other born in Asia/Africa (2nd generation) — that is, Israelis of mixed ethnic origin — constitute only about 2% of the population. This figure underestimates their share due to data limitations in this study.

In the study by Cohen et al. (2021), which was based on 2018 administrative data for individuals aged 25–43, it was found that 54% are Mizrahim, 34% are Ashkenazim, and 12% of Jews are of mixed ethnic origin. This finding applies as well to 2nd and 3rd generation native Israelis.¹⁴ In another study, based on the 2015–2016 European Social Survey for respondents aged 15 and over, 8% of participants (12% of all native-born Israelis) were of mixed

12 Changes in the relative sizes of origin groups aged 25–44 are reported in Appendix Table 1.

13 In 2022–2023, the relative size of the group of native-born Israelis whose parents were both born in Israel (3rd generation) aged 25–44 stood at 45% (Appendix Table 1).

14 The algorithm for identifying mixed ethnic origin is based on the parents' continents of birth in the 2nd generation and on the grandparents' continents of birth in the 3rd generation and beyond.

ethnic origin (Lewin-Epstein & Cohen, 2018). The researchers also report generational differences: in the 2nd generation about 6% were of mixed origin, compared to about 20% in the 3rd generation.

The conclusion drawn from both studies is that the overwhelming majority marry within their own origin groups — or, in more colloquial terms, *within their tribe*. From this one can infer that native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Europe/America are overwhelmingly descendants of Europe/America origin, with only a small share of mixed origin. Likewise, those with one parent born in Israel and the other in Asia/Africa are most likely descendants of Asia/Africa origin, with a small mixed-origin minority. It can also be assumed that a relatively small portion of 3rd generation native-born Israelis (both parents born in Israel) are of mixed ethnic origin once the birthplaces of their grandparents are taken into account.

Table 1. Relative size of origin groups, ages 25–64

Origin group	1995	2008–2009	2022–2023
Israel-born: Israel-born parents (3rd generation)	5.9%	14.1%	30.9%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	29.2%	21.2%	14.7%
European/America-born (1st generation)	15.8%	10.7%	7.0%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	13.4%	10.5%	7.7%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	4.4%	6.1%	7.4%
Israel-born: father Israel-born, mother Europe/America-born	1.7%	2.4%	3.1%
Israel-born: mother Israel-born, father Europe/America-born	2.7%	3.7%	4.4%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	42.1%	31.7%	20.0%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	20.4%	9.3%	3.3%
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	21.7%	22.4%	16.6%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	2.9%	6.3%	8.1%
Israel-born: father Israel-born, mother Asia/Africa-born	1.3%	2.3%	2.9%
Israel-born: mother Israel-born, father Asia/Africa-born	1.6%	4.1%	5.2%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	1.8%	2.4%	2.2%
Israel-born: father Europe/America-born, mother Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	1.1%	1.3%	1.2%
Israel-born: father Asia/Africa-born, mother Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	0.7%	1.1%	1.0%
Former Soviet Union immigrants	12.9%	16.4%	14.9%
Ethiopian immigrants	0.8%	1.4%	1.4%

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Findings

Trends in education level

This section examines changes over time in the education levels of the different origin groups. In particular, it analyzes the changes in individuals' educational attainment according to their highest certificate. The categories are: (1) less than a Bagrut certificate; (2) Bagrut certificate; (3) post-secondary non-academic certificate; (4) academic degree.

Before beginning the discussion of the findings, it is important to clarify two key points:

1. Analysis of the education level data showed that the distribution of educational attainment among native-born Israelis with a father born in Israel and a mother born in Europe/America is similar to that of those with a mother born in Israel and a father born in Europe/America. Accordingly, henceforth these two groups are combined into a single "native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Europe/America" category. For the same reasons, native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Asia/Africa are merged into one group. Likewise, native-born Israelis with a mother born in Europe/America and a father born in Asia/Africa are combined with those whose father was born in Europe/America and mother in Asia/Africa (2nd generation mixed ethnic origin). Appendix Table 2 reports the results prior to these groupings.
2. The data were also analyzed excluding the Haredi population, and a detailed discussion appears in the Appendix. The main conclusions remain unchanged when Haredim are excluded, and therefore, in this section and throughout the study, the results are presented for the entire population.

Figure 1 presents the distribution of education levels among individuals aged 25–64, based on a multivariate analysis (multinomial regression) controlling for gender and age.¹⁵ Several salient points emerge from the regression results:

15 The multinomial regression coefficients are reported in Appendix Table 3. In addition, a model controlling for district of residence was estimated, and the results do not differ from the model without this control. The main conclusions for the population aged 25–44 remain unchanged (Appendix Figure 1).

- Over the past three decades, the population's education level has risen markedly: the predicted probability of holding an academic degree increased from 22% at the start of the period to 45% in recent years. Concurrently, the share of individuals predicted not to have obtained a Bagrut certificate fell from 47% to 23%. At the same time, the proportion holding only a post-secondary non-academic certificate declined from 16% to 13%.
- In the mid-1990s, substantial education level gaps existed between Europe/America origin groups and Asia/Africa origin groups (1st and 2nd generations). A similar gap appeared among native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Europe/America versus those with one parent born in Israel and the other in Asia/Africa (generation 2.5). Among immigrants from the FSU, the predicted shares with an academic degree and a post-secondary certificate peaked (44% and 23%, respectively). At the opposite extreme, 89% of Ethiopian immigrants lacked a Bagrut certificate.

After three decades, educational attainment gaps between origin groups have narrowed. The data show a consistent expansion of higher education in the population (except among immigrants from the FSU). However, the relative rate of expansion was higher among those of Asia/Africa origin (1st and 2nd generations) and among native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Asia/Africa (generation 2.5). Among Ethiopian immigrants — whose starting point in the mid-1990s was the lowest — substantial changes occurred: a marked increase in Bagrut eligibility, alongside growth in the share eligible for an academic degree from 3% to 12%, with most of the gains taking place over the last 15 years. Nevertheless, Ethiopian immigrants remain at a significant educational disadvantage compared to other origin groups.

- Education levels of native-born Israelis of mixed ethnic origin (2nd generation) are intermediate — higher than those of Asia/Africa origin (1st and 2nd generations) and lower than those of Europe/America origin (1st and 2nd generations).

Figure 1. Predicted probabilities of education levels, ages 25–64
Percent

Note: The predicted probabilities are calculated based on a multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Trends in higher education

The previous section described the process of narrowing educational attainment gaps between origin groups, and which driven by faster rate of expansion of higher education among those groups that had previously been underrepresented among academic degree holders. This section focuses on the development of higher education, with particular attention to gender differences and to changes in the share of advanced-degree holders (master's and doctoral) among all academic degree holders.

Table 2 presents the predicted share of higher education degree holders among individuals aged 25–64, based on a multivariate analysis (logistic regression) controlling for gender and age.¹⁶ Table 3 reports the representation index, defined as the ratio of a given origin group's weight among academic-degree holders to its weight in the overall population.¹⁷ A ratio greater than 1 indicates that the group is overrepresented among academic degree holders relative to its population share, whereas a ratio less than 1 indicates underrepresentation. Several salient points emerge from these tables:

- The expansion of higher education characterized all origin groups except immigrants from the FSU. Among women, the increase was larger (from 22% to 50%) compared to men (from 22% to 39%).¹⁸
- The data show high rates of higher education among individuals from European/American origin (first and 2nd generations), native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Europe/America, and immigrants from the FSU. In these groups, the representation index has

16 The logistic-regression coefficients are reported in Appendix Table 4. In addition, a model controlling for district of residence was estimated, and the results do not differ from the model without this control. The main conclusions for the population aged 25–44 remain unchanged (Appendix Tables 5 and 6).

17 For example, if a given origin group's share among academic degree holders is 16% and its share in the overall population is 10%, then the representation index equals 1.6 (16% ÷ 10%).

18 It should be noted that in the 1980s the share of academic degree holders was higher among men than among women; nevertheless, the rate of expansion of higher education among women was faster (Appendix Table 7).

always exceeded 1 but has declined over time. This decline reflects a faster rate of educational expansion among other origin groups: Asia/Africa origin (first and 2nd generations), native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Asia/Africa, native-born Israelis of mixed ethnic origin, and Ethiopian immigrants. Within these latter groups, the changes among women were particularly pronounced. As a result, their representation indices rose over time, indicating a narrowing of gaps between origin groups in higher education attainment.

- The data for native-born Israelis (3rd generation) require separate consideration due to this group's relative size in the population and its heterogeneity. The findings show a marked increase in the share of higher-education degree holders within this group, accompanied by a decline in its representation index among all higher education holders. This outcome reflects the rapid expansion of higher education among groups that were previously underrepresented among academic degree holders.

Table 2. Predicted share of those with an academic education, ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	27%	55%	26%	43%	26%	49%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	30%	56%	33%	47%	32%	52%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	31%	58%	33%	46%	32%	52%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	34%	64%	34%	49%	34%	57%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	7%	25%	9%	22%	8%	23%
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	9%	37%	9%	25%	9%	31%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	16%	53%	16%	34%	16%	44%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	19%	53%	19%	43%	19%	48%
FSU immigrant	44%	51%	43%	41%	44%	46%
Ethiopian immigrant	3%	13%	4%	11%	3%	12%
Total	22%	50%	22%	39%	22%	45%

Note: The predicted probabilities are calculated based on the multivariate analysis. In Columns 1–4, the estimates control for age; in Columns 5–6, they control for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Table 3. Representation index of origin groups among academic degree holders, ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	1.22	1.10	1.15	1.11	1.19	1.10
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	1.38	1.12	1.46	1.22	1.42	1.16
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	1.40	1.16	1.47	1.21	1.44	1.18
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	1.52	1.27	1.51	1.28	1.51	1.27
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	0.32	0.50	0.40	0.58	0.36	0.52
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	0.39	0.73	0.40	0.64	0.39	0.69
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	0.74	1.05	0.71	0.89	0.73	0.98
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	0.87	1.05	0.83	1.12	0.85	1.08
FSU immigrant	2.01	1.01	1.90	1.06	1.96	1.03
Ethiopian immigrant	0.12	0.26	0.16	0.29	0.14	0.27

Note: The calculations in this table are based on the results in Table 2 above.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Another aspect of the expansion of higher education concerns changes in the relative share of advanced degree holders (master's and doctoral) among all academic degree holders (Table 4).¹⁹ A number of points emerge from the table:

- In the mid-1990s, among academic degree holders the share of advanced degree holders was higher for men than for women (47% vs 41%), but over time this reversed: men's share of advanced-degree holders fell to 39%, while women's remained essentially unchanged. This reflects that the expansion of higher education among men was driven more by growth in bachelor's degrees than by growth in advanced degrees, whereas among women the rates of increase for bachelor's and advanced degrees were similar.²⁰
- In the mid-1990s, immigrants from the FSU exhibited very high shares of advanced degree holders among academic degree holders (69% of women and 75% of men). European/American born origin group also exceeded the overall average and also for both men and women, while other origin groups were below average.

Three decades later, the FSU share of advanced degree holders fell sharply (from 72% to 46, as many early immigrants retired and were replaced by a younger cohort whose educational profile resembles that of native Israelis. A particularly notable increase in the share of advanced degree holders was observed among native-born Israelis with parents from Asia/Africa (2nd generation), native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and one in Asia/Africa (generation 2.5), native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and one in Europe/America (generation 2.5), and native-born Israelis of mixed origin — with changes among women notably more pronounced.

19 The main conclusions for the population aged 25–44 remain unchanged (Appendix Table 8).

20 An examination of the data from the 1980s shows that the expansion of higher education among men was accompanied by a faster relative increase in bachelor's degree holders compared to advanced degree holders. Among women, by contrast, the rate of increase in advanced degree holders was faster than that of bachelor's degree holders (Appendix Table 7).

Table 4. Share of advanced degree holders out of all academic degree holders, among ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	22%	36%	28%	34%	25%	35%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	45%	46%	53%	46%	49%	46%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	28%	41%	37%	41%	33%	41%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	23%	46%	31%	39%	27%	43%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	32%	32%	37%	35%	35%	33%
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	19%	42%	24%	37%	21%	40%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	18%	37%	27%	34%	22%	36%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	21%	41%	30%	42%	25%	41%
FSU immigrant	69%	45%	75%	49%	72%	46%
Ethiopian immigrant		24%		33%		28%
Total	41%	40%	47%	39%	44%	40%

Note: Empty cells denote small sample size.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

The data presented in this section indicate that higher education has expanded across most origin groups. The fastest expansion rate was observed in those origin groups that have historically exhibited lower participation in higher education.²¹

Trends in study major choice

The previous section addressed educational attainment differences between origin groups and the choice to pursue advanced degrees. This section examines differences between origin groups in the choice of academic study major among academic degree holders.

The choice of study major shapes the skills accumulated during one's studies, long-term earnings, and social prestige. Krill et al. (2016) found that study major explains 20% of the variance in earnings among 29–39-year-olds. The highest wage premiums were in computer science, engineering, and medicine, while the lowest premiums were among graduates of the arts, psychology, architecture, and the humanities.

The literature shows that when higher education expands, new opportunities open for all population groups. Nonetheless, additional mechanisms of inequality can arise in higher education participation stemming from institutional quality and study major choice. Socioeconomically advantaged groups are best positioned to seize new educational opportunities, thereby preserving their relative socioeconomic advantage. Conversely, students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds tend to enroll in less prestigious institutions and less lucrative fields of study (Ayalon & Yogev, 2005).

21 It is important to emphasize that this conclusion rests on changes measured relative to the chosen indicator. For example, according to Table 2, when comparing first-generation Europe/America natives to 1st-generation Asia/Africa natives, the share holding a bachelor's degree rose from 32% to 52% in the first group and from 8% to 23% in the second. In relative terms, expansion was much faster in the second group (an increase of about 188% versus about 63%). However, if the indicator had been the share without an academic degree, the conclusion would differ: in the first group that share fell from 68% to 48% (a relative decline of about 29%), whereas in the second group it declined from 92% to 77% (a relative decline of about 16%).

In the Israeli context, Cohen et al. (2021) documented differences in higher education quality by type of academic institution. They found that among Mizrahim aged 25–43, a higher proportion earned their degrees at colleges compared to Ashkenazim, whereas Ashkenazim held the advantage among university graduates. The data available for this study do not distinguish university from college attendance, and therefore institutional quality differences are not addressed here.

Differences in study major choice can also be inferred from existing filtering mechanisms such as Bagrut performance and the psychometric exam score. Based on data from the National Institute for Testing and Evaluation (NITE), Figure 2 depicts the average psychometric score among Hebrew-language examinees by the father's place of birth (Europe/America; Asia/Africa; Israel).

Students whose fathers were born in Asia/Africa scored lower on average than those whose fathers were born in Europe/America or in Israel. As a result, among Asia/Africa origin examinees, the choice of prestigious fields is, on average, more limited than among other origin groups. Nevertheless, the data also show a narrowing of score gaps between Asia/Africa origin examinees and those from other origin groups.²²

Figure 2. Psychometric exam scores among those tested in Hebrew, by father's continent of birth

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: National Institute for Testing and Evaluation (various years)

22 It is possible that this result is also reflected among third-generation native-born Israelis — descendants of Asia/Africa immigrants — who cannot be identified in the NITE data.

To obtain a broad picture of study major choice across origin groups, data from the CBS Social Survey were used. The data analysis focuses on individuals holding an academic degree and those who, at the time of the Social Survey, were in the midst of their studies. The results are shown in Table 5. That table shows the predicted distribution of study majors by origin group, based on a multinomial regression controlling for gender and age.²³ Gender differences in study major choice are well documented in previous research (Feniger et al., 2013; Fuchs, 2016). Separate results for men and women appear in Appendix Tables 10 and 11.

Due to sample-size constraints in the Social Survey, 1st-generation Europe/America natives were combined with 2nd-generation Israelis whose parents were born in Europe/America into a single *Europe/America origin (1st and 2nd generations) group*. Similarly, 1st-generation Asia/Africa natives were combined with 2nd-generation Israelis whose parents were born in Asia/Africa into an *Asia/Africa origin (1st and 2nd generations) group*. Native-born Israelis of mixed ethnic origin were excluded from this analysis because of low number of observations. Several key points emerge from the results:

- Immigrants from the FSU are markedly overrepresented in STEM and medicine.²⁴ The cohort that arrived in the 1990s was highly educated, especially in these disciplines. The share of these fields has declined over time among FSU immigrants but remains above the share of these fields in the overall population. These trends hold for both women and men separately (Appendix Tables 10 and 11).

In the broader context, a substantial proportion of immigrants from the FSU obtained their education abroad.²⁵ Many found themselves overqualified — where one’s level of education exceeds the requirements of their job — partly due to limited language skills (Bleikh, 2020).

23 The multinomial regression coefficients are reported in Appendix Table 9. In addition, a model controlling for district of residence was estimated, and the results do not differ from the model without this control.

24 STEM fields (science, technology, engineering, mathematics) include physical sciences, biological sciences, mathematics, statistics, computer science, engineering, and architecture.

25 According to Social Survey data, in the early 2000s, about 10% of immigrants from the FSU aged 25–64 holding an academic degree reported that they obtained their education in Israel; in recent years, this figure stands at approximately 45%.

Among those FSU immigrants who completed their STEM and medical studies in Israel, the rates remain high compared to other origin groups. It can thus be said that the younger generation educated in Israel largely continues their parents' tradition of investing in STEM and medicine.²⁶

- The remaining data align with the main findings from Figure 2 above. As noted, examinees whose fathers were born in Europe/America score higher on the psychometric exam than those whose fathers were born in Asia/Africa, which increases their chances of admission to more prestigious and more lucrative fields of study. Indeed, the table shows that among European/American descent (1st and 2nd generations) and native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Europe/America (generation 2.5), higher shares enter STEM and medicine compared to Asian/African origin (1st and 2nd generations) and native-born Israelis with one parent born in Israel and the other in Asia/Africa (generation 2.5). In contrast, Asian/African origin and their generation 2.5 counterparts are more likely to pursue fields such as business administration and, to a lesser extent, law — a pattern especially pronounced among men.

Asia/Africa origin groups (1st and 2nd generations) choose studies in education and teaching professions in higher numbers, which are predominantly female.

- Among 3rd-generation native-born Israelis, the predicted share entering STEM and medicine rose from 24% to 27%, with this upward trend apparent for both men and women.

Notably, the gap in STEM and medicine enrollment between European/American origin (1st and 2nd generations) and Asian/African origin (1st and 2nd generations) narrowed over time — from an 11 percentage point difference to 7 points. It can be cautiously inferred that 3rd-generation native-born Israelis of Europe/America versus Asia/Africa descent are likely to exhibit smaller differences in field of study choice than in the past.

26 According to recent Social Survey data for individuals aged 25–44 who obtained their academic education in Israel, approximately 36% of immigrants from the FSU hold degrees in STEM and medicine, compared with about 27% among other origin groups. At the same time, among immigrants from the FSU aged 25–44 who obtained their education abroad, about 51% held degrees in STEM and medicine in 2007–2009, compared with about 31% in recent years.

Table 5. Predicted probability of a study major, among ages 25–64

	Humanities, literature, languages, arts	Education, teacher training	Paramedical professions	Social sciences	Law	Business, management sciences	Science	Engineering	Medicine	Mathematics, statistics, computer science
2007–2009										
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	11.8%	16.6%	3.3%	21.7%	6.3%	16.0%	4.1%	14.4%	2.1%	3.7%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	13.9%	12.3%	3.7%	19.0%	7.1%	12.6%	5.7%	17.4%	3.9%	4.5%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	11.7%	12.4%	3.3%	20.8%	8.8%	13.2%	7.0%	16.1%	2.0%	4.6%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	12.3%	19.5%	2.5%	19.8%	5.5%	19.9%	4.2%	13.3%	1.0%	1.9%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Asia/ Africa-born (generation 2.5)	10.7%	14.5%	2.0%	24.8%	7.0%	15.6%	3.1%	15.0%	1.4%	5.9%
FSU immigrant	8.3%	12.2%	2.4%	12.3%	2.0%	9.2%	8.6%	34.0%	5.9%	5.1%
Total	11.6%	14.4%	3.0%	18.9%	5.8%	14.3%	5.7%	19.0%	3.2%	4.1%
2021–2023										
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	8.5%	16.8%	3.3%	19.8%	8.5%	15.8%	5.0%	14.6%	2.5%	5.1%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	6.3%	13.8%	6.2%	21.7%	7.6%	15.4%	4.9%	15.1%	3.3%	5.7%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	8.9%	14.2%	2.3%	18.9%	6.0%	17.9%	4.2%	16.1%	3.1%	8.5%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	7.0%	17.8%	3.7%	23.6%	6.2%	19.7%	2.8%	13.5%	1.5%	4.3%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Asia/ Africa-born (generation 2.5)	5.0%	19.5%	1.9%	20.1%	9.2%	18.2%	3.1%	14.6%	1.7%	6.6%
FSU immigrant	5.6%	8.0%	5.2%	17.7%	5.1%	12.9%	5.9%	26.8%	4.8%	8.0%
Total	7.1%	15.0%	3.9%	20.3%	7.3%	16.5%	4.6%	16.5%	2.8%	6.0%

Note: The predicted probability is calculated based on the multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey (various years)

Summary

This study examined trends in educational attainment among origin groups within Israel's Jewish population. Historically, educational — and more broadly, socioeconomic — gaps between origin groups emerged already in the early years of the State. According to the research literature, investment in education increases employment and earnings, contributes to social mobility, and reduces social and economic disparities in areas such as income, health, and poverty.

The study focused on changes over time in several indicators related to education: educational levels (less than a Bagrut certificate, a Bagrut certificate, post-secondary non-academic certificates, academic degrees); higher education, including changes in the share of those with advanced degrees; and the choice of academic study majors. The available database allowed analysis over three decades (1995–2023). This period is particularly notable due to demographic changes in Jewish society and in the education system over the past thirty years: demographically, most individuals in the Jewish population today are 2nd- and 3rd-generation descendants of Jews from Asia/Africa and Europe/America. In addition, there is a large immigrant population from the FSU and a smaller group from Ethiopia. During this period, reforms were introduced to the Bagrut exams aimed at increasing certificate rates and reducing educational gaps between weaker and stronger population groups. At the same time, the higher education system expanded through the establishment of colleges (both public and private), which met the demand for academic studies that universities alone could not accommodate.

The results show that educational attainment increased over the years across all origin groups in Jewish society. At the lower end of the spectrum, Bagrut certificate rates increased, and at the upper end, the share of academic degree holders rose. However, the rate of change was more notable among origin groups that historically had lower education levels. For example, among Israeli-born individuals with parents from Asia/Africa (2nd generation) aged 25–64, there has been a significant increase in high school graduation rates over the last three decades, and as a result, the percentage of university graduates has risen by 22 percentage points (from 9% to 31%) — an increase of 3.4 times. For comparison, among Israel-born individuals whose parents are from Europe/America (2nd generation), who started out with a much stronger initial position, there was an increase in Bagrut eligibility alongside a 20 percentage point

increase in the share with an academic degree (from 32% to 52%) — 1.6 times greater. Similarly, larger changes were seen among Israel-born individuals with one parent born in Asia/Africa and one parent born in Israel, compared to those with one parent born in Europe/America and one parent born in Israel.

Among Ethiopian Israelis — the weakest group by all parameters examined — in the mid-1990s, 89% did not have a Bagrut certificate. Three decades later, this share dropped to 56%, and the share with an academic degree rose from 3% to 12%.

The narrowing of gaps between origin groups was also evident in the changing share of individuals with advanced degrees (master's and doctorate) among all academics. Notably, changes were more pronounced among women than among men.

Regarding the choice of academic study majors, it is first important to consider the screening mechanism — the psychometric exam. Over time, the average psychometric score of students whose father is from Europe/America has been higher than that of students whose father is from Asia/Africa, but the gap has narrowed. As a result, over the years, the likelihood that students of Asia/Africa origin are accepted to higher paying, more prestigious study majors has increased, although it still remains lower compared to students of European/American origin.

Differences in psychometric scores between origin groups translate into disparities in academic major selection. For example, in fields with higher earning potential, immigrants from the FSU, individuals from European/American origin, and Israeli-born individuals with one parent from Israel and one from Europe/America tend to pursue STEM and medicine professions at higher rates. In contrast, individuals from Asian/African origin and Israeli-born individuals with one parent from Israel and one from Asia/Africa (especially men) are more likely to pursue fields such as business administration and law. Nonetheless, over the past fifteen years, the gap between 2nd-generation individuals from Asia/Africa and Europe/America in their participation in STEM and medicine has narrowed.

In sum, the findings of this study point to an overall trend of narrowing educational gaps between origin groups. However, this does not mean that further effort is unnecessary. To ensure continued progress in reducing educational gaps, the state can increase affirmative support for schools serving

populations from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. A study of high school funding found that the cumulative effect of the Nurture and periphery indices on budget variability was modest.²⁷ This suggests that it may be appropriate to increase the weight of the differentiation and periphery-based components so they better reflect students' socioeconomic backgrounds (Blass & Bleikh, 2024). Ben-David and Kimhi (2020) emphasize the importance of focusing on mathematics education in the periphery, as math achievement is the strongest predictor of labor market success among Bagrut subjects.

The increase in education among origin groups that historically lacked educational opportunities and their returns has contributed to narrowing disposable income gaps between households (Dahan, 2016). However, disposable income also determines a household's ability to invest in children's education. Viewed across generations, education and income are mutually dependent: education influences earning potential, and parental income enables investment in children's education — creating a cycle.

Finally, the literature shows that differences in education between origin groups are largely explained by parents' socioeconomic background. However, parents' decisions also matter: whether to invest their spare income in education — or in something else.

27 The Nurture index is a composite measure that ranks schools according to the socioeconomic status of their students and serves as a central tool of the Ministry of Education in the allocation of resources among schools.

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Appendix

Appendix Table 1. Relative size of origin groups, among ages 25–44

	1995	2008–2009	2022–2023
Israel-born: Israel-born parents (3rd generation)	7.8%	21.8%	44.6%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	22.9%	14.2%	11.9%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	10.0%	6.7%	5.5%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	12.9%	7.5%	6.5%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	5.7%	7.9%	7.7%
Israel-born: father Israel-born, mother Europe/America-born	2.1%	3.3%	3.4%
Israel-born: mother Israel-born, father Europe/America-born	3.7%	4.6%	4.3%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	43.7%	25.7%	9.4%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	10.6%	2.8%	2.2%
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	33.1%	22.9%	7.3%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	3.9%	9.8%	9.2%
Israel-born: father Israel-born, mother Asia/Africa-born	1.8%	3.4%	3.3%
Israel-born: mother Israel-born, father Asia/Africa-born	2.1%	6.4%	5.9%
Israel born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	2.7%	3.1%	1.5%
Israel-born: father Europe/America-born, mother Asia/Africa-born	1.7%	1.6%	0.6%
Israel-born: father Asia/Africa-born, mother Europe/America-born	1.0%	1.5%	0.8%
FSU immigrants	12.3%	15.3%	13.5%
Ethiopian immigrants	0.9%	1.8%	1.6%

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 2. Predicted probability of education levels, among ages 25–64

	1995				2022–2023			
	Less than a Bagrut	Bagrut certificate	Post-secondary certificate	Academic degree	Less than a Bagrut	Bagrut certificate	Post-secondary certificate	Academic degree
Israel-born: Israel-born parents	41%	16%	16%	26%	21%	18%	12%	49%
Europe/America-born	33%	17%	19%	31%	21%	16%	11%	52%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born	31%	16%	21%	32%	16%	18%	13%	52%
Israel-born: father Israel-born, mother Europe/America-born	33%	15%	18%	34%	15%	15%	12%	58%
Israel-born: mother Israel-born, father Europe/America-born	31%	16%	19%	34%	17%	16%	12%	56%
Asia/Africa-born	68%	12%	11%	8%	47%	19%	11%	23%
Israel-born: Asia/Africa-born parents	67%	12%	12%	8%	35%	23%	12%	31%
Israel-born: father Israel-born, mother Asia/Africa-born	55%	16%	13%	16%	21%	20%	12%	46%
Israel-born: mother Israel-born, father Asia/Africa-born	55%	15%	14%	16%	25%	22%	11%	43%
Israel-born: mother Asia/Africa-born, father Europe/America-born	49%	16%	17%	18%	22%	20%	10%	48%
Israel-born: mother Europe/America-born, father Asia/Africa-born	48%	17%	16%	20%	19%	21%	12%	48%
FSU immigrant	19%	14%	23%	44%	16%	22%	17%	46%
Ethiopian immigrant	89%	4%	5%	3%	56%	26%	6%	12%
Total	47%	14%	16%	22%	23%	20%	13%	45%

Note: Predicted probability is calculated on the basis of a multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 3. Multinomial regression: Probability estimates for education level choice, among ages 25–64

	1995			2008–2009			2022–2023		
	Bagrut vs Less than Bagrut	Post-secondary vs Less than Bagrut	Academic vs Less than Bagrut	Bagrut vs Less than Bagrut	Post-secondary vs Less than Bagrut	Academic vs Less than Bagrut	Bagrut vs Less than Bagrut	Post-secondary vs Less than Bagrut	Academic vs Less than Bagrut
Women	0.308***	0.308***	0.1000***	0.440***	0.493***	0.521***	0.576***	0.528***	0.850***
Age (Reference group: 25–29)									
30–34	-0.353***	0.0427**	0.119***	-0.617***	0.263***	0.434***	-0.659***	0.151***	0.545***
35–44	-0.736***	-0.0822***	-0.105***	-0.702***	0.380***	0.405***	-0.717***	0.178***	0.708***
45–54	-1.102***	-0.203***	-0.274***	-1.070***	0.101**	0.105***	-0.800***	0.243***	0.611***
55–59	-1.389***	-0.498***	-0.652***	-1.383***	-0.0555	-0.101**	-0.867***	0.238***	0.382***
60–64	-1.714***	-0.992***	-1.173***	-1.509***	-0.163***	-0.234***	-0.924***	0.0493	0.258***
Origin group (Reference group: Israel-born, parents Israel-born [3rd generation])									
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	0.264***	0.427***	0.422***	0.364***	0.524***	0.274***	-0.104**	-0.058	0.0648*
Israel-born: Europe/America-born parents (2nd generation)	0.228***	0.544***	0.474***	0.215***	0.462***	0.308***	0.206***	0.352***	0.316***
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	0.246***	0.431***	0.525***	0.309***	0.398***	0.629***	0.105**	0.283***	0.431***
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	-0.859***	-0.893***	-1.688***	-0.646***	-0.758***	-1.633***	-0.796***	-0.919***	-1.609***
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	-0.789***	-0.761***	-1.638***	-0.541***	-0.562***	-1.317***	-0.286***	-0.527***	-1.007***
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	-0.364***	-0.438***	-0.801***	-0.210***	-0.201***	-0.547***	0.0256	-0.139***	-0.239***
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	-0.160***	-0.149***	-0.509***	0.00514	-0.0644	-0.232***	0.127*	-0.0572	-0.00254
FSU immigrant	0.645***	1.174***	1.303***	0.983***	1.505***	0.892***	0.477***	0.654***	0.229***
Ethiopian immigrant	-2.312***	-2.042***	-2.973***	-1.654***	-2.235***	-3.098***	-0.639***	-1.749***	-2.460***
Constant	-0.322***	-0.903***	-0.260***	0.138***	-1.062***	-0.0751***	0.247***	-0.949***	-0.0463*
Number of observations		40,3625			98,953			195,487	
pseudo R ²		0.086			0.069			0.045	

Significance level: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01. | Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Figure 1. Predicted probabilities of education level, among ages 25–44
Percent

Note: The predicted probabilities are calculated based on a multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 4. Logistic regression: Probability of having attained higher education, among ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Women					-0.051***	0.517***
Age (Reference group: 25–29)						
30–34	0.022	0.686***	0.451***	1.011***	0.216***	0.810***
35–44	-0.150***	0.774***	0.435***	1.282***	0.120***	0.988***
45–54	-0.277***	0.593***	0.452***	1.296***	0.065***	0.901***
55–59	-0.567***	0.389***	0.259***	1.085***	-0.179***	0.694***
60–64	-0.978***	0.278***	-0.0476*	1.095***	-0.537***	0.636***
Origin group (Reference group: Israel-born, parents Israel-born [3rd generation])						
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	0.172***	0.0463	0.330***	0.189***	0.249***	0.114***
Israel-born: Europe/America-born parents (2nd generation)	0.198***	0.130***	0.349***	0.162***	0.274***	0.149***
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	0.323***	0.367***	0.387***	0.280***	0.350***	0.321***
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	-1.604***	-1.310***	-1.278***	-0.964***	-1.427***	-1.187***
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	-1.363***	-0.759***	-1.284***	-0.842***	-1.322***	-0.799***
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	-0.642***	-0.0834**	-0.612***	-0.366***	-0.621***	-0.217***
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	-0.443***	-0.0953*	-0.427***	0.0158	-0.431***	-0.0341
FSU immigrant	0.782***	-0.173***	0.762***	-0.082***	0.774***	-0.136***
Ethiopian immigrant	-2.594***	-2.102***	-2.260***	-1.798***	-2.419***	-1.983***
Constant	-0.773***	-0.320***	-1.381***	-1.358***	-1.029***	-1.058***
Number of observations	209,298	103,717	194,327	91,770	403,625	195,487
pseudo R ²	0.114	0.042	0.102	0.047	0.105	0.051

Significance level: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 5. Predicted share of academic degree holders, among ages 25–44

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	32%	54%	28%	39%	30%	47%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	36%	58%	35%	47%	35%	52%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	34%	60%	31%	39%	33%	50%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	38%	62%	34%	45%	36%	54%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	10%	24%	11%	19%	10%	21%
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	10%	49%	9%	29%	10%	39%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	20%	56%	17%	33%	18%	45%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	21%	58%	18%	46%	20%	52%
FSU immigrant	44%	50%	40%	38%	42%	44%
Ethiopian immigrant	3%	18%	3%	13%	3%	15%
Total	24%	53%	22%	38%	23%	45%

Note: Predicted probabilities are calculated on the basis of a multivariate analysis (logistic regression). Columns 1–4 are with controls for age and Columns 5–6 are with controls for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 6. Representation index of origin groups among academic degree holders, among ages 25–44

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	1.33	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.31	1.03
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	1.50	1.08	1.08	1.25	1.55	1.15
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	1.40	1.12	1.12	1.04	1.43	1.09
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	1.60	1.17	1.17	1.20	1.59	1.18
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	0.41	0.45	0.45	0.49	0.45	0.45
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	0.42	0.93	0.93	0.76	0.42	0.85
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	0.81	1.05	1.05	0.88	0.79	0.98
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	0.90	1.09	1.09	1.23	0.87	1.15
FSU immigrant	1.83	0.94	0.94	1.01	1.84	0.97
Ethiopian immigrant	0.12	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.13	0.33

Note: The calculations in this table are based on the results in Appendix Table 5 above.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 7. Share of academic degree holders by gender and the highest degree attained, among ages 25–64

	Women			Men		
	BA	MA or higher	Total	BA	MA or higher	Total
1983	7%	3%	10%	8%	6%	14%
1995	13%	9%	22%	12%	11%	22%
2000	18%	10%	28%	15%	11%	26%
2005	20%	12%	32%	17%	12%	28%
2010	24%	13%	37%	18%	12%	30%
2015	27%	16%	43%	22%	13%	35%
2020	29%	18%	47%	23%	14%	37%
2023	30%	20%	50%	24%	15%	38%

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census, 1983, 1995

Appendix Table 8. Share of advanced degree holders out of all academic degree holders, among ages 25–44

	Women		Men		Total	
	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023	1995	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	21%	31%	26%	28%	23%	30%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	38%	41%	46%	42%	42%	41%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	24%	33%	32%	26%	28%	30%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	21%	40%	28%	32%	24%	36%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	27%	24%	32%	26%	30%	25%
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	18%	34%	23%	29%	20%	32%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	18%	32%	24%	29%	20%	31%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	19%	35%	28%	37%	23%	36%
FSU immigrant	68%	39%	74%	39%	71%	39%
Ethiopian immigrant		25%		28%		26%
Total	35%	34%	41%	31%	38%	33%

Note: Empty cells denote small sample size.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 9 (continued). Multinomial regression: Probability estimates for study major choice, among ages 25–64

	Humanities, literature, languages, arts	Education, teacher training	Paramedical professions	Social sciences	Law	Business, management science	Sciences	Engineering	Medicine
2021–2023									
Women	1.749***	2.884***	2.594***	1.641***	1.063***	0.826***	1.117***	0.0214	0.904***
Age (Reference group: 25–29)									
30–34	0.61	0.169	-0.448	0.455	0.819*	0.745**	0.431	-0.0805	0.3
35–39	0.895**	0.347	0.117	0.505*	1.214***	0.934***	0.663	0.215	0.566
40–44	1.542***	0.835**	0.870*	1.156***	1.685***	1.565***	1.264***	0.483	0.907
45–49	1.153***	0.518*	-0.138	0.719**	1.229***	0.948***	0.558	0.00725	0.920*
50–54	1.594***	0.904**	1.017**	0.739*	1.312***	1.416***	0.997*	0.827**	1.508**
55–59	1.932***	1.089**	0.716	1.107**	1.545***	1.191**	1.193**	0.644	2.087***
60–64	2.080***	0.737	0.255	0.789*	1.310**	0.864*	1.479**	0.715	1.721***
Origin group (Reference group: Israel-born, parents Israel-born [3rd generation])									
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	-0.403	-0.314	0.512	-0.0194	-0.211	-0.135	-0.133	-0.0661	0.154
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	-0.505	-0.752**	-0.968*	-0.598*	-0.890**	-0.406	-0.719*	-0.407	-0.336
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	-0.00342	0.257	0.295	0.369	-0.132	0.407	-0.4	0.0898	-0.359
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	-0.804*	-0.123	-0.825	-0.245	-0.172	-0.114	-0.735	-0.251	-0.686
FSU immigrant	-0.986***	-1.378***	-0.171	-0.684**	-1.039***	-0.716**	-0.378	0.17	0.143
Constant	-1.458***	-1.017***	-2.160***	-0.034	-1.019***	-0.108	-1.202***	0.775***	-1.951***
Number of observations	4,489								
pseudo R ²	0.06								

Note: The coefficients in each column are relative to the baseline group — mathematics, statistics, and computer science.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey (various years)

Appendix Table 10. Predicted probability of a study major among women, ages 25–64

	Humanities, literature, languages, arts	Education, teacher training	Paramedical professions	Social sciences	Law	Business, management sciences	Science	Engineering	Medicine	Mathematics, statistics, computer science
2007–2009										
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	16.6%	24.4%	5.8%	24.6%	4.7%	10.9%	2.0%	7.6%	0.7%	2.7%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	18.9%	19.0%	5.2%	21.7%	5.9%	10.8%	7.3%	6.5%	2.4%	2.3%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	14.2%	20.7%	5.7%	19.5%	6.8%	13.4%	6.9%	7.1%	1.4%	4.2%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	14.5%	29.9%	4.2%	19.0%	4.9%	16.0%	3.8%	5.2%	1.3%	1.2%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	12.9%	22.2%	3.7%	29.8%	5.1%	11.8%	2.5%	6.3%	0.9%	4.8%
FSU immigrant	11.4%	16.3%	3.1%	17.0%	2.6%	12.2%	8.7%	18.7%	6.5%	3.5%
Total	15.1%	21.7%	4.6%	21.2%	4.9%	12.4%	5.7%	8.9%	2.8%	2.7%
2021–2023										
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	9.2%	26.1%	5.0%	23.0%	7.3%	12.2%	4.4%	7.5%	2.5%	2.6%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	7.6%	20.8%	9.4%	23.2%	7.1%	14.2%	4.6%	7.8%	2.8%	2.6%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	12.4%	22.3%	3.0%	22.3%	5.9%	12.9%	4.8%	10.5%	1.1%	5.0%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	8.8%	27.0%	5.6%	27.2%	5.9%	15.1%	3.0%	5.0%	1.0%	1.5%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	6.0%	31.7%	2.2%	24.8%	6.6%	14.5%	3.2%	7.3%	1.6%	2.1%
FSU immigrant	6.9%	10.4%	7.6%	23.3%	6.3%	14.4%	5.8%	15.4%	4.6%	5.3%
Total	8.5%	22.9%	5.7%	23.8%	6.7%	13.6%	4.5%	8.7%	2.5%	3.1%

Note: The predicted probability is calculated based on the multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey (various years)

Appendix Table 11. Predicted probability of a study major among men, ages 25–64

	Humanities, literature, languages, arts	Education, teacher training	Paramedical professions	Social sciences	Law	Business, management sciences	Science	Engineering	Medicine	Mathematics, statistics, computer science
2007–2009										
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	5.9%	6.8%	0.5%	18.3%	8.0%	22.2%	6.8%	22.6%	3.7%	5.0%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	7.8%	4.1%	1.8%	15.7%	8.6%	14.6%	4.1%	30.4%	5.8%	7.3%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	8.8%	2.2%	0.4%	22.4%	11.7%	12.4%	7.2%	27.1%	2.6%	5.2%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	9.6%	6.7%	0.4%	20.8%	6.3%	24.9%	4.8%	23.2%	0.7%	2.8%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	8.2%	5.2%	0.0%	17.5%	9.7%	20.5%	4.0%	25.5%	1.9%	7.5%
FSU immigrant	4.6%	7.6%	1.6%	6.3%	1.3%	5.7%	8.3%	53.2%	4.7%	6.8%
Total	7.2%	5.4%	1.0%	16.0%	7.0%	16.6%	5.8%	31.3%	3.8%	5.8%
2021–2023										
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	7.5%	4.6%	1.1%	15.4%	10.1%	20.6%	5.8%	23.9%	2.5%	8.5%
European/American descent (1st and 2nd generation)	4.5%	4.5%	2.0%	19.7%	8.2%	17.0%	5.4%	24.9%	4.0%	9.8%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	4.7%	3.8%	1.1%	14.8%	6.0%	23.3%	3.5%	24.1%	5.3%	13.4%
Asian/African descent (1st and 2nd generation)	4.7%	5.6%	1.1%	19.1%	6.5%	25.6%	2.5%	24.5%	2.2%	8.3%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born, a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	3.5%	3.2%	1.4%	13.9%	13.1%	23.0%	3.2%	24.3%	1.7%	12.9%
FSU immigrant	3.9%	5.2%	2.2%	9.9%	3.6%	11.1%	6.0%	42.2%	4.9%	11.0%
Total	5.2%	4.4%	1.4%	15.5%	8.0%	20.4%	4.8%	27.1%	3.3%	9.9%

Note: The predicted probability is calculated based on the multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey (various years)

An examination of the results excluding the Haredi population

To what extent are the findings presented here sensitive to differences in the share of Haredim within the origin groups? To address this question, the findings were examined excluding the Haredi population. Identification of the Haredi population based on self-reporting was added to the Labor Force Survey in 2014. In earlier years, the Haredi population was identified differently, based on three criteria: (1) all household members were identified as Haredi if the head of household was a man whose last educational institution was a yeshiva; (2) all household members were identified as Haredi if the head of household was a woman whose spouse's last educational institution was a yeshiva; (3) individuals who studied in a yeshiva in households not defined as Haredi under the first two criteria.

The 1995 Population Census data do not allow for identifying the Haredi population according to these definitions. The analysis in this section is therefore based on Labor Force Survey data from the 2000s. According to Labor Force Survey data, the share of Haredim among the Jewish population (including "Others") aged 25–64 rose from around 4% in 2000–2001 to around 11% in 2022–2023. This implies that the bias in the distribution of education when excluding the Haredi population is likely to be greater in recent years, due to the larger share of Haredim in the population.

Another point worth noting is the distribution of the Haredi population across origin groups. In general, most Haredim — regardless of origin group — were born in Israel (over 80% in recent years), and according to streams, the majority of Haredim belong to groups primarily composed of individuals of European/American origin and their descendants: 34% Lithuanian, 29% Hasidic, and 4% Chabad, compared with 33% Sephardic (Regev & Miletzky, 2023).

Appendix Figures 2 and 3 illustrate this. The distribution of education levels in the total population in the early 2000s is almost identical to the distribution excluding the Haredi population. The picture changes somewhat when looking at more recent data. The reason, as noted, is the increase in the share of Haredim in the population.

As noted, the distribution of Haredim within origin groups is not uniform, and this is reflected in the results for the following origin groups: Israel-born individuals with Israel-born parents, individuals born in Europe/America, Israel-born individuals with parents born in Europe/America, and Israel-born individuals with one parent born in Israel and the other in Europe/America.

These trends also hold for the tables describing changes in the share of those with an academic degree and the share holding advanced degrees among all degree holders (Appendix Tables 12–17).

Nonetheless, the main conclusion of the current analysis excluding the Haredi population remains unchanged. The gaps in education levels between origin groups have narrowed. The data indicate a consistent expansion of higher education across all origin groups (except for FSU immigrants). However, the pace of expansion was faster among individuals of Asian/African origin (1st and 2nd generations), among Israel-born individuals with one Israel-born parent and one parent born in Asia/Africa (generation 2.5), and among Israel-born individuals with parents of mixed ethnic origin.

Appendix Figure 2. Predicted probabilities for education levels, among ages 25–64 Percent

Note: The predicted probabilities are calculated based on a multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years)

Appendix Figure 3. Predicted probability for education level, among ages 25–64, excluding Haredim
Percent

Note: The predicted probabilities are calculated based on a multivariate analysis (multinomial regression), controlling for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years)

Appendix Table 12. Predicted probability of holding an academic degree, among ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	37%	55%	31%	43%	34%	49%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	37%	56%	36%	47%	36%	52%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	39%	58%	37%	46%	38%	52%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	45%	64%	38%	49%	42%	57%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	8%	25%	10%	22%	9%	23%
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	13%	37%	11%	25%	12%	31%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	24%	53%	22%	34%	23%	44%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	27%	53%	24%	43%	26%	48%
FSU immigrant	47%	51%	43%	41%	45%	46%
Ethiopian immigrant	4%	13%	8%	11%	5%	12%
Total	29%	50%	26%	39%	27%	45%

Note: Predicted probabilities are calculated on the basis of a multivariate analysis (logistic regression). Columns 1–4 are with controls for age and Columns 5–6 are with controls for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 13. Predicted share of those holding an academic degree, among ages 25–64, excluding Haredim

	Women		Men		Total	
	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	40%	60%	35%	49%	37%	54%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	38%	59%	37%	52%	38%	56%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	41%	62%	39%	51%	40%	57%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	49%	70%	42%	57%	45%	63%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	8%	25%	11%	23%	9%	24%
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	13%	38%	12%	26%	13%	32%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	25%	55%	22%	36%	24%	46%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	27%	55%	25%	46%	26%	51%
FSU immigrant	47%	51%	43%	41%	45%	46%
Ethiopian immigrant	4%	13%	8%	11%	5%	12%
Total	29%	53%	27%	42%	28%	47%

Note: Predicted probabilities are calculated on the basis of a multivariate analysis (logistic regression). Columns 1–4 are with controls for age and Columns 5–6 are with controls for gender and age.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years); Population Census 1995

Appendix Table 14. Representation index of origin groups among academic degree holders, among ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	1.28	1.10	1.19	1.11	1.23	1.10
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	1.29	1.12	1.36	1.22	1.32	1.16
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	1.35	1.16	1.40	1.21	1.38	1.18
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	1.59	1.27	1.45	1.28	1.52	1.27
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	0.27	0.50	0.40	0.58	0.33	0.52
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	0.45	0.73	0.44	0.64	0.45	0.69
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	0.85	1.05	0.83	0.89	0.84	0.98
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	0.95	1.05	0.93	1.12	0.94	1.08
FSU immigrant	1.64	1.01	1.63	1.06	1.63	1.03
Ethiopian immigrant	0.13	0.26	0.29	0.29	0.20	0.27

Note: The calculations in this table are based on the results in Appendix Table 12 above.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years)

Appendix Table 15. Representation index of origin groups among academic degree holders, among ages 25–64, excluding Haredim

	Women		Men		Total	
	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	1.35	1.14	1.27	1.16	1.31	1.15
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	1.29	1.13	1.36	1.24	1.32	1.17
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	1.38	1.18	1.43	1.22	1.40	1.20
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	1.66	1.33	1.54	1.35	1.60	1.34
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	0.27	0.48	0.39	0.55	0.33	0.50
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	0.45	0.72	0.43	0.63	0.44	0.68
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	0.84	1.05	0.82	0.87	0.83	0.97
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	0.93	1.05	0.92	1.09	0.93	1.07
FSU immigrant	1.60	0.97	1.57	0.98	1.58	0.97
Ethiopian immigrant	0.12	0.25	0.28	0.27	0.19	0.25

Note: The calculations in this table are based on the results in Appendix Table 13 above.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years)

Appendix Table 16. Share of advanced degree holders out of all academic degree holders, among ages 25–64

	Women		Men		Total	
	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	25%	36%	32%	34%	28%	35%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	41%	46%	51%	46%	46%	46%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	32%	41%	41%	41%	36%	41%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	27%	46%	32%	39%	29%	43%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	25%	32%	34%	35%	30%	33%
Israel-born: parents Asia/Africa-born (2nd generation)	20%	42%	21%	37%	20%	40%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	19%	37%	27%	34%	23%	36%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	24%	41%	23%	42%	23%	41%
FSU immigrant	57%	45%	68%	49%	62%	46%
Ethiopian immigrant		24%		33%		28%
Total	37%	40%	45%	38%	41%	40%

Note: Empty cells denote small sample size.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years)

Appendix Table 17. Share of advanced degree holders out of all academic degree holders, among ages 25–64, excluding Haredim

	Women		Men		Total	
	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023	2000–2001	2022–2023
Israel-born: parents Israel-born (3rd generation)	25%	38%	32%	34%	28%	36%
Europe/America-born (1st generation)	42%	47%	51%	47%	46%	47%
Israel-born: parents Europe/America-born (2nd generation)	32%	42%	41%	41%	37%	42%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Europe/America-born (generation 2.5)	27%	49%	32%	40%	29%	45%
Asia/Africa-born (1st generation)	25%	32%	34%	35%	30%	33%
Israel-born: parents Asia/ Africa-born (2nd generation)	20%	43%	21%	37%	20%	40%
Israel-born: a parent Israel-born and a parent Asia/Africa-born (generation 2.5)	19%	38%	27%	35%	23%	36%
Israel-born, mixed descent (2nd generation)	24%	43%	22%	41%	23%	42%
FSU immigrant	57%	45%	68%	49%	62%	47%
Ethiopian immigrant		24%		31%		27%
Total	38%	42%	45%	39%	41%	41%

Note: Empty cells denote small sample size.

Source: Haim Bleikh and Gil S. Epstein, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Labor Force Survey (various years)